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Introduction

1.1 INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES IN THE CARIBBEAN NETHERLANDS: RESENTED YET NEGLECTED

This dissertation starts from a sense of wonder at the lack of action regarding a widely resented environmental problem. Inhabitants of Saba and St. Eustatius (commonly known as Statia) are vocal in their dissatisfaction with the invasive alien Coralita vine (*Antigonon leptopus* (Hook. & Arn.)), which originates from Mexico and has been spread all around the world, covering significant areas on the islands. It is infamous for covering vast areas rapidly, and for being very hard to remove due to tuberous roots that grow up to a few meters deep (Burke and diTommaso 2011). Coralita smothers native vegetation and overgrows nesting sites of iguanas, exacerbating the hardship of the endangered *Iguana delicatissima* (van der Burg et al. 2012). Coralita's presence on the islands was first officially recorded in 1902 (Boldingh 1909), and on Statia the plant is estimated to cover 15% to 20% of the island (van der Burg et al. 2012). These are predominantly former agricultural areas but also land on the borders of the national parks. On Saba, Coralita is creeping up Mount Scenery, which is crowned with a unique elfin forest and attracts many tourists (van de Kerkhof et al. 2014). Due to Coralita's pink flowers, it is a very visible phenomenon, and during fieldwork people frequently expressed their discontent regarding the vine covering such large areas and overgrowing their yards. Yet, this professed discontent is rarely accompanied by action to contain the vine. Which differs from the challenge regarding most invasive alien species, involving opposing stakes or a lack of awareness hampering action.

Species that are alien to an ecosystem and behave in an invasive manner have been deemed the second biggest threat to biodiversity, after habitat degradation (Pejchar and Mooney 2009). Next to that, they can incur great economic costs, by damaging agriculture, infrastructure and human health (Pimentel et al. 2005, Shine et al. 2010). Invasive alien species (IAS) are therefore tightly controlled in some countries, such as Australia and New Zealand (Koch et al. 2016) or Hawaii (Daehler et al. 2004), but the European Union only adopted the first regulation on invasive species in 2014 (European Parliament and Council of the European Union 2014). IAS can be globally appreciated (e.g., coffee, wheat or rice), the center of heated debate (grey squirrels in European urban parks), mostly ignored (summer lilacs in Europe) or commonly hated (Japanese knotweed in Europe) (Bertolino and Genovesi 2003, Koch et al. 2016). Management of IAS is not a straightforward endeavor, since large uncertainties are often involved, as well as many different stakes, and typically cooperation from a wide array of actors is required. Combined with the substantial potential damages incurred, IAS make for a significant governance challenge, and one that is increasingly receiving attention. This dissertation seeks to add to the governance literature on invasive alien species, by studying the lack of management and policy regarding an invasive alien species on two semi-sovereign Caribbean islands, Saba and St. Eustatius.

Islands are argued to be especially vulnerable to IAS, since their ecosystems are more fragile. That enhances both the chances of establishment of an alien and exacerbates its impacts (Kairo et al. 2003, Reaser et al. 2007). Although the exact dynamics remain disputed (Sax 2008, see Vilà et al. 2011), it is fair to say that there is a lot to be lost on Caribbean islands. They make up one of the world's 25 global biodiversity hotspots, with about 60% of the region's 12,000 plant species being endemic (Mittermeier et al. 1998, Kairo et al. 2003). This natural richness is an important attraction for the tourists who make up a significant part of the economy on many Caribbean islands. The already vulnerable agricultural sector on Caribbean islands is threatened by IAS as well. But despite the risks posed by invasive aliens and the assets to be protected, inertia in terms of policy and management exists on these two islands of the Caribbean Netherlands. Much research has been conducted (see Coblenz 1980, Jongman et al. 2010, Smith et al. 2014) and the expired Caribbean nature policy plan 2013–2017 mentions IAS as an important threat and encourages islands to develop policy (Ministerie van EZ 2013), but to no avail. With most land privately owned and an absence of spatial planning ordinances (Schoenmaeckers 2010), there is no view of any policy development soon either. And this policy inertia is compounded by a lack of management action on the part of private land owners, despite the general dismay Coralita is regarded with. Sabans and Statians are very aware and weary of the vine, and yet, there is policy and management inertia. This paradoxical concurrence of resentment yet neglect regarding an environmental issue, is the focus of this dissertation. Policy and management inertia are analyzed and strived to resolve, meanwhile eliciting defining characteristics of environmental problems such as Coralita on Saba and Statia. Thus, the dissertation offers insights useful for other cases of inertia as well.

1.2 GOVERNANCE CHALLENGE OF INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES

The inertia this dissertation focuses on pertains to an invasive alien species (IAS). In this section the governance challenge posed by IAS is explored: what are IAS, and why are they so challenging to deal with?

1.2.1 What is an invasive alien species?

Many different terms exist: invasive, alien, exotic, non-native, introduced, pest – as diverse as the terms used for species that do not belong, is the contestation surrounding them. This dissertation uses the phrasing “invasive alien species”, which comprises two elements: a “not from here” and a “causing disturbance” element.

Synonyms of the former are terms such as alien, foreign, exotic, non-native, and introduced, all implying a distinction between original and non-original elements of an

ecosystem. This leads some to argue that the field of invasion biology is rooted in xenophobia (e.g., Valéry et al. 2009, Davis et al. 2011). Indeed, when looking at the language used in invasive species literature, phrasings of aggressive invaders that show explosive growth and need to be combated are not uncommon:“(...) military metaphors and exaggerated claims of impending harm to help convey the message that introduced species are the enemies of man and nature.” (Davis et al. 2011, 153). In response, others argue that such objections are unhelpful diversions of scientific attention, while invasions do pose a significant problem to biodiversity (Simberloff 2011). Whether xenophobic or not, a common view is that the spread of aliens started with either the Silk routes or Columbus traveling to the Americas (Leuven 2017). While for the European Netherlands a rather arbitrary date to distinguish between authentic and non-authentic species, for the Caribbean the arrival of Columbus indeed meant the start of major movements of organisms and goods. Apart from looking at whether a species was present in an ecosystem originally, one could focus on the role of humans in introductions. In the view of Richardson et al. (2000), a species is alien when its presence in an area is due to either intentional or accidental introduction through human activity. Leaving this debate as it is, following either definition, Coralita counts as an alien species on Saba and Statia.

The second part of the term “invasive alien” is highly normative, focusing on the damage an alien species can do to an ecosystem or area it is introduced into. Ecosystems are perceived as systems with a dynamic balance, meaning that they can adapt to changes within a certain bandwidth of resilience (Allen and Holling 2010). A species is invasive when it disturbs this balance and pushes the system beyond its limits, which can be assessed by the abundance or rate of spread of the species. This view has two implications, the first being that a native species may become invasive at some point as well, and linked to this, a debate on whether invasive species should be seen as the drivers of change, or the passengers of change (Bauer 2012, Garrock et al. 2014). When conceiving of invasion as a phenomenon caused by changes in the environment that allow it to proliferate (such as by Valéry et al. 2008), invasive species are passengers of change. Likewise, when looking at invasion as resulting from transportation into a novel environment, the vector of transportation is the real culprit. To dodge the need to disentangle such processes, one can also simply look at the impacts of the alien species once it has established, as will be addressed later. But does this mean that every species with negative impacts is an invasive species, and when does a native species that has negative impacts become an invasive species? On the Caribbean islands where this research takes place, Elephant ear (*Philodendron giganteum*) invades abandoned farmland and the understory of the native forest (van der Burg et al. 2012). Davis et al. (2011) argue that “Nativeness is not a sign of evolutionary fitness or of a species having positive effects,” pointing out that the most damaging insect in North America at the time was the native mountain pine beetle. Challenging this is research such as by Paolucci et al.

(2013) showing that introduced predators are more likely to coincide with decreasing prey populations than native predators. Richardson et al. (2000) keep it even simpler by deeming a plant invasive when it spreads more than 100 meters in less than 50 years if seed-dispersed, or more than 6 meters in 3 years for those spreading via roots. The definition of an invasive alien will likely remain contested for as long as it is the topic of research.

The foregoing discussion clearly shows that even among ecologists, invasive alien species spur much debate and little agreement. While attention for IAS for a long time remained confined to the field of ecology, it is nowadays recognized as inherently social as well (Shackleton, et al. 2019). For example, Richardson et al. state: “Humans cause invasions, humans perceive invasions, and humans must decide whether, when, where and how to manage invasions.” (Richardson et al. 2008, 297). Put differently: there are no invasive species without humans. And as the next section will show, precisely this entanglement of the social and ecological dimension make for a complex governance challenge.

1.2.2 Why are invasive aliens a complex governance challenge?

While debates regarding IAS persist, the movement of species across the globe continues at an ever increasing rate. The spread of aliens surged during the industrial revolutions with railways, canals and highways, and the migration of 50 million Europeans to colonies abroad (Hulme 2009). But the real increase took place during the past 35 years, during what has been called the Anthropocene (Crutzen 2002) or Homogenocene (Samways (1999) in: Verbrugge 2014). Anthropocene refers to the current era in which planet Earth is dominated by humans, and Homogenocene refers specifically to the extinction of many species due to humans. Although there are too many unknowns to either corroborate or refute the claim that a “McDonaldization of ecosystems” will eventually occur (Lövei 1997), the potential damage of IAS is enormous (Pejchar and Mooney 2009). The latest United Nations IPBES report lists invasive aliens as one of the main drivers of degradation of natural life (Díaz et al. 2019). In that light, the increased invasion rate is very worrisome, and dealing with invasive alien species is an urgent but complex matter. Urgent, because tipping points can be exceeded, resulting in a regime shift and making it impossible to return to an earlier state (Gaertner et al. 2014). Complex, because the process, impacts and solutions of an invasion by an alien species are not easily understood and to a certain extent unknowable (Blackburn et al. 2011). Here three elements of the invasive alien species governance challenge are discussed: assessing the impacts, understanding people’s perceptions, and getting people involved.

1.2.2.1 Assessment of effects: impacts and risks

As mentioned before, negative impacts are often central to the definition of what is and is not an IAS, for example in the framework presented by Marbuah et al. (2014), but also in the definition of the Convention on Biological Diversity: “Invasive alien species (IAS) are species whose introduction and/or spread outside their natural past or present distribution threatens biological diversity.” (UN 1992). Of course, whether impacts of a species are negative or positive can be source of contention (Blackburn et al. 2014, Woodford et al. 2016, Bacher et al. 2017, Zengeya et al. 2017). For example, exotic salmonids were introduced in many rivers in the Southern hemisphere, offering great sport fishing opportunities but endangering local fish species (De Leaniz et al. 2010). The *Acacia maerensii* tree, or black wattle, was introduced to South Africa in the mid-19th century and by now covers about 2.5 million hectares. While it is commercially valuable for timber, pulp and firewood, it has negative effects on water resources and biodiversity (De Wit et al. 2001). For these species, management measures are a source of great conflict, involving the weighing of positive and negative impacts (Novoa et al. 2016).

Often, establishing the effects of a given species is far from straightforward. One approach is to look at the ecosystem services no longer provided or the disservices delivered, due to an alien’s establishment (Vaz et al. 2017). Methodologies based on this are for example EICAT (ecological impact classification of alien taxa (Blackburn et al. 2014)), SEICAT (socio-economic impact classification of alien taxa (Bacher et al. 2017)), and the Harmonia+ and Pandora+ protocol (D’hondt et al. 2014). The identified impacts can then be monetized (Born et al. 2005). Although monetizing impacts might work to raise awareness, it is also a very complex endeavor and results in conspicuous discrepancies such as a €12 billion a year estimate of damages for the EU versus €120 billion a year for the USA (Pimentel et al. 2005, Shine et al. 2010). These differences can be attributed to different accounting mechanisms, the inclusion of social costs, or whether preventive measures are accounted for (Bacher et al. 2017). Also, many objections have been raised to attaching financial value to nature, such as it being unethical, counterproductive, and unable to capture all values (e.g. Norgaard 2010, Spangenberg et al. 2015).

But for many species, the impacts on ecosystems are far from known, since what happens post-invasion is not a straightforward process: both the invading and the resident species will evolve in response to one another, which may affect abiotic processes in the system, in turn affecting the species, resulting in an infinite spiral of adjustments (Buckley 2017). These cascading effects are poorly understood, since metrics like impact-abundance relationships are not yet well understood (Sofaer et al. 2018). Given such profound uncertainties, IAS are often characterized as an environmental risk, for which risk analysis should be applied (Simberloff et al. 2005, Hulme 2006). This generally distinguishes between risk assessment and risk management, the former aiming to establish the risk of a species, i.e., the chance of it occurring and the impacts it would have. Risk

management looks at the risk that is acceptable, and as such involves a value judgement regarding the risk (Liu et al. 2011). Therefore, efforts have been made to enhance the role of stakeholders in risk analysis, following a wider trend within environmental sciences. For example, Liu et al. (2010, 2011) developed a Deliberative Multi-Criteria Analysis framework in which a jury is employed to weigh uncertainties, or to incorporate values and stakes in the decision-making. In a similar manner, Vanderhoeven et al. (2017) propose peer review and consensus building approaches, and increasing transparency regarding uncertainty in order to enhance risk assessments. Despite acknowledging the profound uncertainty involved with IAS, these approaches aim to prioritize species, sites, pathways and management approaches based on the quantification and valuation of risk. Uncertainties are assumed to pertain to the occurrence and effects of invasions, not to the valuation of invasions. For example, Liu et al. (2011) speak of epistemic and linguistic uncertainties, and of the need to incorporate different value judgements through participatory approaches. But the jury they propose to establish is supposed to assuage such uncertainties and ambiguities, and reach a decision in spite of it. One of the main arguments that will be put forward in this dissertation is that in some cases there is not so much a contestation over different valuations, but rather an absence of valuations due to latent problem perceptions. This will be addressed elaborately in chapter 3, and the next section relays the current understanding of how valuations of IAS come about.

1.2.2.2 *An individual's perceptions*

Quite some work has been done in the field of environmental psychology regarding IAS, exploring the way people perceive a given species and what determines their willingness to manage. The hierarchy postulated by Azjen's Theory of Planned Behavior (1988) presenting values and beliefs as the basis on which attitudes are produced, which subsequently determine behavior, is generally accepted. Concordantly, work to *understand* people's behavior regarding IAS has focused on their values and beliefs, whereas work to *influence* people's behavior typically focusses on their attitudes, assuming that the value and belief systems are too durable to be adjusted.

Regarding values and beliefs, a distinction can be made between held and assigned values. Held values are enduring and belong to the realm of world views (Slimak and Dietz 2006), value or attitude orientations (Sharp et al. 2011) and core beliefs (Sabatier 1988). Similar to beliefs, a held value "...reflects the most basic elements of cognition that facilitate preferences and induce action." (Van Riper and Kyle 2014, 375). Opposed to this, assigned values are perceived qualities of environmental resources based on benefits provided to people, and inherently unstable. They are more fluid than held values and directly influence behavior, while being influenced by the foundation of held values through which people interpret the world around them (Sharp et al. 2011, Van Riper and

Kyle 2014). The held beliefs have been found to be good indicators of support for environmental management. For example, environmental attitude orientations appeared indicative of support for invasive species management among visitors to Cumberland Island National Seashore in Georgia, USA (Sharp et al. 2011). Images of human-nature relations were found to be good predictors of support for non-native species management among the Dutch public (Verbrugge et al. 2013). In Ontario, Canada and Scotland, beliefs about invasive species regarding e.g., their impact and nativeness were found to be indicative of attitudes towards managing a species (Fischer et al. 2014). Several typologies with corresponding survey questions are used to investigate people's values, such as the New Environmental Paradigm by Dunlap et al. (2000), nature representations (Vanderhoeven et al. 2011), images of nature (Buijs et al. 2009), the Connectedness to Nature scale (Mayer and Frantz 2004) and the Images on Human-Nature relationships scale (de Groot 2012). As mentioned earlier, these values are typically understood not to be open to adjustments, but very influential. Conflicting value systems can result in contention between different stakeholder groups, and when communication about IAS and management efforts is not in line with extant value systems, it will not be accepted (Kalnicky et al. 2019). A "backfire effect" has even been reported, when messages challenge strongly held beliefs and result in even stronger support for misconceptions (Wald et al. 2019).

More dynamic are people's attitudes regarding IAS, which are affected by their knowledge and awareness of IAS, and their interaction with the species. Typically, the more direct the experience with an IAS and knowledge of how to control it, the more likely people are willing to control it (Shackleton and Shackleton 2016). But the opposite can happen too: when an IAS has a long presence in a community, people may have grown accustomed to them. Negative effects can become downplayed ("habituation effect"), or the species may have taken on an important role or service in the ecosystem (Kalnicky et al. 2019, Lewis et al. 2019). Lewis et al. (2019) argue that these should be taken into account, and thus decision-making should be based on two elements: people's attitudes regarding the species, and (dis)services delivered by the species in that given ecosystem.

Overall, understanding of people's perceptions regarding IAS is limited. See for example Shackleton and Shackleton (2017) or Heger et al. (2013) for attempts at assessing such perceptions, and the recent attempt at establishing a framework of factors affecting perceptions (Shackleton et al. 2019). This framework shows a wide array of factors involved, but gives little insight into their interaction, let alone their parametrization. Not understanding people's perceptions hampers their involvement in decision-making and management of a species, and can result in resistance (Sharp et al. 2011, Shackleton and Shackleton 2016). But even if a full understanding of people's perceptions could at some point be gleaned, then there are still some other factors at play before people will actually act and get involved with decision-making or policy development, which is the third element of the governance challenge IAS pose.

1.2.2.3 *Stakeholder involvement in management*

Let us assume for a moment that the impacts of an IAS have been established and people's perceptions are understood, resulting in the decision to manage the species. Note that it is increasingly acknowledged that in some cases an IAS is beyond eradication or resources are too limited, and an approach of "living with" can best be adopted (Head et al. 2015). But even when there are still options left, management is not a straightforward affair, and much more than simply deciding whether to eradicate, contain or suppress a species (e.g., Zimmerman et al. 2011). For example, risk assessments such as Harmonia⁺ (D'hondt et al. 2014) or SEICAT (Bacher et al. 2017) are very elaborate, as is setting up proper pre-border control (Koch et al. 2016). And when looking at the IUCN "Guidelines for invasive species planning and management on islands" (2018), one finds that risk assessment and pre-border control are only a small part of the actions needed across ten thematic areas divided over three themes, ranging from building capacity, to monitoring changes, to post-management restoration. Moreover, management of IAS requires full cooperation of a wide array of actors, and as soon as one falters, the efforts of others can prove fruitless (Caplat and Coutts 2011).

Involving stakeholders with policy development and decision-making is increasingly recognized as crucial for the management of invasive alien species (IAS). Hulme (2006) calls public perception and stakeholder involvement "(...) arguably the most important yet most often overlooked (...)" aspect of IAS management (Hulme 2006, 845). Since then, involvement of stakeholders has received ample attention in literature, both arguing the why and how of involvement. The why is for example argued from a conflict resolution perspective: if people do not feel involved in decision-making regarding IAS management, they might refuse to cooperate at all (Crowley et al. 2017). Differences in valuation of IAS' impacts need to be accounted for in management decisions (García-Llorente et al. 2008, Shackleton et al. 2015). Next to affecting the management of IAS, humans also affect the occurrence of the problem itself. One, because people use and move organisms thereby mediating invasions, and two, because in the definition of invasiveness people's perceptions are key (Kueffer 2010).

An important challenge for stakeholder involvement is presented by the aforementioned divergent values, exacerbated by different interests, which results in opposing valuations of IAS and their impacts (e.g., Hulme 2006, García-Llorente et al. 2008). A large part of stakeholder involvement is thus to somehow match these different stakes. Next to that, social dynamics like trust, peer pressure and behavioral control beliefs mediate involvement. For example, Niemiec et al. (2016) draw attention to efficacy and behavioral control beliefs: do people believe they on their own or as a group can make a difference? Also important are social norms, such as peer pressure, mutual support and information sharing (Graham 2013). Social learning, good relationships and trust are therefore very important (Graham and Rogers 2017). Trust needs to be both horizontal – will my neigh-

bor deliver? – and vertical – will the government or nature manager deliver? (Marshall et al. 2016). To meet these needs, community-based polycentricity, co-management and co-design and partnerships for IAS management are called for (Marshall et al. 2016, Shackleton et al. 2019). Thus, from a stakeholder involvement perspective, the main challenges of IAS management lie with conflicting stakes and building social capital to allow for stakeholder involvement in decision-making and policy development.

1.2.2.4 *Knowledge gap*

The foregoing sketched the governance challenge of IAS as comprising three elements: the assessment of ambiguous and uncertain impacts, the different values and attitudes of people affecting that assessment, and the involvement of these people with decision-making and policy development. Much progress has been made in establishing the impacts of a species, while taking values and attitudes into account. Frameworks and methods abound for identifying stakeholders and involving them in decision-making, in order to improve management. For example, articles look at private landowners (Niemiec et al. 2016), urban garden owners (Shackleton and Shackleton 2016) or horticulturalists (Vanderhoeven et al. 2011) and how to get them to cooperate. But less researched, are cases of invasive alien species where there is no decision-making taking place; where there are no stakeholders, nor management efforts to involve them in. All the above-mentioned insights, e.g., into how to build trust, reach compromise and account for differences, were gained from situations where there was something happening. Either there were management plans but they required land owners' cooperation, or there were conflicts between actors with opposing stakes. But we lack understanding of cases where all this is largely absent, which is the knowledge gap this dissertation aims to fill. A case of an invasive alien species for which stakeholders are unknown, and policy and management are lacking, will be thoroughly analyzed and strived to resolve. In the following section, a research aim and question are formulated, after which the methodological approach is outlined for reaching that aim and answering that question.

1.3 RESEARCH STRATEGY

1.3.1 Research aim and question

From the review above, the intricacy of the governance challenge posed by invasive alien species becomes clear. Also sketched was the propensity of environmental governance literature to address cases where something is happening: there are stakeholders, management efforts or decision-making processes taking place that could be enhanced. Such articles start out by discussing the invasive species of interest, elaborating on its negative impacts and demonstrating why a currently uninvolved actor's cooperation

is crucial for successful management of the species. By analyzing what is at stake for that actor, the decision-making, policy development or management efforts regarding that species can be enhanced. This dissertation takes the opposite approach, by analyzing inertia pertaining to policy and management. Instead of asking how to enhance management activities, it asks why there are none; instead of identifying what is at stake for the local community, it explores a lack of stakes. By understanding a lack of policy and management action, insights are obtained into how to encourage action. Thus, the **research aim** of this dissertation is to:

Foster decision-making on invasive alien species, by understanding policy and management inertia

The inertia focused on pertains to the invasive alien Coralita vine (*Antigonon leptopus*) on the Dutch Caribbean islands of Saba and St. Eustatius. Despite its apparent rapid spread causing nuisance to every landowner and gardener, little to nothing is being done to manage the vine. European Union policies on invasive alien species do not apply on these islands, but the (expired) Caribbean nature policy plan 2013–2017 does identify IAS as an important threat and encourages the individual islands to develop policy (Ministerie van EZ 2013). This has not been done so far, and the reasons for this policy inertia will be researched in this dissertation.

However, Sullivan et al. (2017) show how oftentimes when *de jure* institutions are falling short, *de facto* institutions fill the gap for IAS management. In this case, the government and nature management organization are not fulfilling their formal role regarding the management of Coralita, but what about the community who has the plant growing on their land? Community action is an important element on both islands, given the large share of privately owned land (Schoenmaeckers 2010). Yet, despite the species being regarded a clear nuisance by almost every landowner, little management is undertaken by the community. The smothering vine poses a clear threat to agriculture, which given the peaking food prices in the wake of the 2017 hurricanes Irma and Maria and the increased push from the national government for increased self-sufficiency, is gaining importance (Ministerie van BZK 2018). These dynamics could have moved the community to act, but no *de facto* institution has picked up the gauntlet so far. This management inertia is researched as well, and avenues for lifting the policy and management inertia will be explored. The **research question** of this dissertation is thus:

How can the policy and management inertia regarding the invasive alien Coralita vine on Saba and St. Eustatius be explained and resolved?

Taking the opposite route – starting from what is not, in order to determine what is – is one of the elements that sets this dissertation apart and makes it valuable for environmental governance literature. Also, some methodological contributions are made in chapter 3 and 4, which can be of use to environmental issues beyond invasive alien species. Regarding invasive alien species literature, the dissertation contributes by broadening the scope from stakeholders to the wider governance arrangement. Stakeholder positions are analyzed, but additionally the governance configuration that mediates the development of policy, and the community's practices that mediate management activities are analyzed as well. From a societal perspective, the added value of this dissertation lies in addressing the highly challenging topic of invasive alien species, of which the importance has been elaborately discussed in section 1.2. But also in pointing at a specific set of environmental governance problems for which conventional decision-making approaches are not suitable, and offering alternatives. Let us now take a closer look at the case central to achieving these aims.

1.3.2 Case background: Saba and St. Eustatius

This dissertation focuses on two islands: Saba and St. Eustatius (commonly known as Statia), part of the Caribbean Netherlands (see Figure 1). *Saba* measures 13 km² and as such is the smallest of the two. It is the northernmost island of the volcanic inner arc of the Lesser Antilles and was formed about 500,000 years ago, making it younger than other islands in this region. The peak of the dormant volcano, surrounded by a few domes, rises out above the Caribbean sea to 872 meters. There is still a lot of geothermal activity, and because of the steep rocky coastline, erosion is an issue in many places. The slopes are steep, sometimes exceeding 60° or are even nearly vertical, making agriculture difficult. Although precise figures concerning Saba's economy are lacking, tourism is generally considered to be a major source of income and the main source of labor for its 2200 inhabitants, after the government and the medical university (van de Kerkhof et al. 2014, de Freitas et al. 2016, CBS 2018). *Statia* is located about 30 km southeast of Saba, has a population of 3300 people and is slightly larger: 21 km². It has a dormant volcano known as The Quill, which forms the highest point of the island at 600 meters. During the colonial period it accommodated about 70 plantations, mainly located on the flat areas in the center of the island. Currently, some agriculture still takes place, but the main economic activity is the oil terminal of the US company NuStar. Two other sources of employment are the local government and tourism (DLG 2011, de Freitas et al. 2012, van de Kerkhof et al. 2014, CBS 2018).

Although located closely to one another, the islands are rather different; both ecologically but also politically. Just like most islands in the Caribbean, they were held by many different colonial powers, until with the first Kingdom Charter of 1954, the islands Saba, St. Eustatius, St. Maarten, Bonaire, Curaçao and Aruba jointly formed the Netherlands

Antilles. In 1986, Aruba seceded, and after approximately 17 years of negotiations, referenda and protests, in 2010 the islands Saba, Bonaire and St. Eustatius became special municipalities of Holland, while St. Maarten and Curaçao became countries within the Kingdom, just like Aruba (Oostindie and Klinkers 2012). Bonaire, Saba and Statia form the Caribbean Netherlands, and are “public bodies according to article 134 of the Dutch Constitution” of the Netherlands (Spies et al. 2015).

Figure 1. Map of the research locations: Saba and St. Eustatius

Although their structure is akin to that of Dutch municipalities, there are important deviations from Dutch law, for example regarding their tax system. Even though the islands are Dutch territory, deviation from Dutch law is allowed by article 1 sub 2 of the Statute of the Kingdom (Kingdom of the Netherlands 1954, Bröring et al. 2008). The original idea was to continue Antillean laws as much as possible, with new laws only for topics that had become the responsibility of the Netherlands, such as health care, education, and international security. Dutch regulation was then supposed to gradually replace Antillean legislation, but this intention appears to have withered. Instead, both sides have paid increasing attention to the specific contexts of the islands that require different laws and regulations (Spies et al. 2015). An anomaly in the configuration is the absence of the provincial tier of government, forcing ministries to directly communicate with municipal government. In theory, the RCN was supposed to serve as a linking pin between both entities, but island governments directly communicate with ministries and Rijkswaterstaat. Chapter 2 will look at the working of this in practice.

The relationships of the Netherlands with Saba and Statia respectively are quite different. Whereas Dutch officials visiting Saba always applaud its cooperative attitude, degree of organization and cooperation with The Hague (The Daily Herald 2018a, GIS Saba 2019), the Netherlands imposed supervision on Statia in 2015 (Van Kerkhof 2015a, Van Kerkhof 2015b), followed by complete overtaking of the government in February 2018 (Den Dool 2018). According to the Netherlands there was a situation of severe neglect of tasks, financial chaos, intimidation and lawlessness. Politicians on Statia openly voice their dismay about Dutch officials and even filed an injunction against the Dutch state. They claimed their right to self-government under the United Nations charter was breached by the Dutch interference, but the court disagreed (The Daily Herald 2018b). It seems likely that the Government Commissioner appointed by The Hague will stay on for at least full two years, and during that time no democratically-elected government is in place on Statia (FD 2019). Given these differences, the islands are addressed separately throughout this dissertation. Chapter 2 addresses Statia, chapter 4 Saba and for chapter 3 data was collected and analyzed separately per island.

Saba and Statia make for a highly suitable case to research an absence of action regarding an invasive species and how to deal with that absence. The small scale of both islands allows for a thorough analysis of the dynamics at play, and thus for gleaning a complete picture. Related themes and actors will quickly surface, and unexpected elements appear. Likewise, trying to make changes to dealings with Coralita might be more easily achievable on such a small scale. Lastly, the differences between the islands offer opportunities for making interesting comparisons, and enhance the external validity of the findings. Thus, despite this dissertation focusing on two small islands in the Caribbean, the findings are applicable to other invasive alien species that are not being dealt with. The next section outlines how the coming chapters contribute to that aim.

1.3.3 Outline of dissertation

This dissertation studies why there is policy and management inertia regarding Coralita, and how this could be resolved. The policy inertia is central to chapter 2, looking at the polycentric governance configuration of the islands and the European Netherlands. Chapter 3 focuses on the identification of stakeholders, despite the limited knowledge about the impacts of Coralita making it hard to articulate stakeholder positions. Chapter 4 looks at the lack of action on the part of the community, both explaining its absence and exploring how to encourage action. In chapter 3 and 4, the inertia regarding Coralita is explained by pointing at its latent problem status, as opposed to a manifest problem status. Chapter 5 seeks to corroborate that claim, by looking into the evolution of problem statuses as well as the action and conflict occurring at each of them, concerning thirteen invasive alien species in the Netherlands. In chapter 6, the findings of the foregoing chapters are synthesized to answer the research question, and recom-

recommendations given for further research. Chapter 7 offers a practice-oriented synthesis, by translating findings obtained during fieldwork and from the foregoing chapters, into hands-on recommendations for management of Coralita on Saba and Statia. Below in Figure 2, the contributions of each chapter to the analytical and action-oriented part of the research question are outlined.

Figure 2. Set-up of the dissertation, with for each chapter indicated what its core contribution is.

1.3.4 Methodology

In this dissertation as well as per chapter, multiple methods were used to collect the data needed for answering the research questions. Mixed methods increase validity of research findings by triangulating data from different sources (Onwuegbuzie et al. 2011, Bryman 2016). Additionally, for some of the chapters methodological considerations are an output: in chapter 3, using Q methodology with a landscape value typology is proposed to elicit latent problem perceptions. In chapter 4, an adjusted version for participatory action research is developed and applied. An overview of the methods applied per chapter can be found in Table 1 below. The elements focused on listed in the far-left column coincide with elements outlined in Figure 2. More elaborate descriptions of the methods can be found in each of the chapters.

Analytical focus	Chapter				Method	Description of method
	2	3	4	5		
Governance configuration					Semi-structured interviews	Semi-structured interviews were conducted for chapter 2 and 4, in which you can find more details on selection of interviewees and questions asked. A semi-structured format worked best for both chapters since it strikes a balance between finding out what you want to know, and what you did not know you wanted to find out. For both chapters there was a framework with variables that needed to be addressed, but also a need for letting interviewees give their own experience of the topic (Galletta and Cross 2013). All questions were therefore open-ended, and respondents were asked for additional thoughts they would like to share (Magnusson and Marecek 2015). All interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed, and in chapter 4 NVivo was used for coding and analysis of the transcripts.
Daily practices of the community						
Governance configuration					Desk research	For every chapter the theoretical section is based on a more or less extensive literature study, into e.g. participatory governance, action research, or typologies of environmental problems based on the uncertainties involved. This served to gauge the theoretical and empirical data available regarding these topics. In chapter 2, 4, and 5 we did a more thorough content analysis of grey literature such as policy documents, scientific reports, newspaper articles, websites and videos. For chapter 2 and 4 this served as a foundation to build on with interviews, whereas in chapter 5 this is the sole source of information.
Daily practices of the community						
Problem status trajectories						
Stakeholder perspectives					Q methodology	Q methodology is combined with a landscape value typology in order to elicit latent problem perceptions, of which details can be found in the chapter.
Daily practices of the community					PPGIS	Public Participatory GIS was used to identify potential pilot areas, based on the presence of, and dislike for, Coralita. PPGIS is used to gather information on individual or community experiences of ecosystem services, to research ecological and social values in tandem, or to evaluate the compatibility of different projected uses of an area (Brown, Greg and Fagerholm 2015). In this dissertation it served to identify areas where people are most worried about Coralita, indicating pilot areas for chapter 4, and part of the management recommendations in chapter 7. Also, a mapping exercise regarding fences and the presence of Coralita was part of chapter 4.
Stakeholder perspectives						
Stakeholder perspectives					Online questionnaire	A small-scale questionnaire was administered on the perceived invincibility of Coralita among Sabans, of which the set-up and results can be found in the Appendix. It served to quantify the perceived invincibility of Coralita, and check if any changes were made by participating in the action research.
Daily practices of the community					Adjusted approach to PAR	An adjusted approach to participatory action research is designed and applied in chapter 4, aimed at being particularly suitable to lift inertia regarding latent environmental problems.

Table 1. Overview of the methods used in this dissertation, per topic of analysis and chapter